

NON-LINEAR BEHAVIORS OF PULTRUDED GFRP COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, the non-linear behaviors of pultruded glass fiber reinforced polymer (GFRP) composites were experimentally investigated. In particular, GFRP short columns and GFRP bolted connections were focused, aiming to evaluate the progressive failure of material in the manner of compression and shear failure. The obtained experimental observations demonstrated that the continued end-section crushing and shear-out failure could lead to the non-linear behaviors of GFRPs after reaching their peak loads. The non-linear behaviors of GFRP composites may be of great value for meeting the design requirement for extreme loading conditions.

KEYWORDS

Pultruded GFRP composites; Non-linear behaviors; Progressive failures; Short Columns; Bolted connections

INTRODUCTION

Pultruded glass fiber reinforced polymer (GFRP) composites have been increasingly adopted in the field of civil engineering worldwide (Vedernikov et al. 2020; Liu et al. 2021). Typical applications of pultruded GFRPs may include pedestrian bridges, cooling towers, wind turbine blades, photovoltaic supports, and many other frame structures (Hollaway 2010; Liu et al. 2020). Those applications, in general, are aimed to take advantages of GFRPs in terms of their high strength- and stiffness-to-weight ratios, excellent corrosion resistance, superior fatigue performance, etc. In civil engineering, the structural members or systems are often required to have certain ductile capacities, which, however, is a commonly-known weakness of pultruded GFRPs. Indeed, pultruded GFRPs are widely reported to behave in a linear-elastic manner up to failure, often in form of a sudden-brittle failure by reaching either strength or stability limit state (Guades et al. 2014; Liu et al. 2019). Evidently, this type of failure mode is not favored in practice, as it permits little time for emergence reaction. In this regard, enabling a ‘non-linear’ structural behavior for pultruded GFRP members or structures may potentially improve their applicability in the field.

In past decades, many studies have actually observed various extent of non-linearities in pultruded GFRPs. The earliest study may date back to 1990s when Mosallam and Bank (1992) conducted a static test on a 1.83-m-high by 2.74-m-wide portal frame constructed with pultruded GFRP I-sections. In this test, non-linear load-deflection and moment-rotation responses were identified, which were attributed to the progressive failure of GFRP profiles (including the connections) as well as local buckling of flexural member. Indeed, progressive failure/damage of material may have a significant impact on the overall structural behavior of GFRP members/structures. Such progressive failure is stemmed from the microscopic composition of GFRPs; that is, cracking in fiber and matrix may progressively propagate along certain directions, thus leading to non-linear behavior of pultruded GFRPs at macroscopic level (Fascetti et al. 2021; Zhu et al. 2023). For instance, a simple joint made with only pultruded GFRPs can exhibit a non-linear behavior, due to the inherent progressive damage of material (Qureshi et al. 2015). Additionally, pultruded GFRPs may exhibit non-linear load-displacement curves due to the progressive damage at web-flange junction when subjected to transverse tensile load (Zhu et al. 2023). Moreover, progressive failure can also be realized by certain structural configurations, such as the mortise-and-tenon joint for pultruded GFRP beams and concrete-filled GFRP columns (Feng et al. 2022). This joint was constructed with multiple types of materials with different mechanical properties and found to show a highly non-linear behavior in terms of the moment-rotation response.

The progressive failure of pultruded GFRPs may be determined by many factors. At microscopic level, the fiber volume fraction, resin matrix, and initial material imperfections (i.e., microcracks and voids)

could affect the progressive failure of GFRPs (Haj-Ali and Kilic 2002). In this case, mechanical properties of those GFRPs with low fiber volume fractions may be greatly controlled by the relatively soft resin matrix that tends to behave in a non-linear manner. On the other hand, at macroscopic level, the progressive failure of GFRPs typically becomes more prominent when subjected to high load/strain level (Xin et al. 2017; Zhang et al. 2018), compressive or shear force (Al-saadi et al. 2019), and/or off-axis loading condition (Haj-Ali and Kilic 2002; Zhang et al. 2018). The high load/strain level could facilitate the microcracks or voids to be further opened-up or closed-off; the compressive or shear strength of GFRPs is dominated by properties of matrix; and the off-axis loading condition could transition the fiber-dominant behavior to matrix-dominant behavior. In general, resin matrix is found to have a relatively greater impact on the non-linear behavior of GFRPs.

In this work, the non-linear behaviors of pultruded GFRP composites are focused with the purpose of further exploring their engineering applicability. Inspired by previous studies, structural behaviors of pultruded GFRP short columns and bolted connections are experimentally investigated, since it is the compressive and shear behaviors of GFRPs that have shown the most prominent non-linearities. In addition, this work adopts the latest pullwound GFRP composites with hybrid roving architectures, thus permitting further investigations on the effect of fiber-matrix architecture on the structural behaviors of GFRPs. Pullwinding process and pullwound GFRP box-sections are shown in Figure 1. A total of five types of GFRPs are addressed in this work, including four pullwound box-sections (denoted as Box-1, -2, -3, and -4), and one pultruded box-section (denoted as Box-5). The mechanical properties of all five GFRPs have been measured in the previous study of present authors, as shown in Table 1, and all the details regarding the materials can be seen in Liu et al. (2023).

Figure 1: Pullwinding process and pullwound box-sections (Liu et al. 2023)

Table 1: Mechanical properties of pullwound and pultruded GFRP profiles (Liu et al. 2023)

Specimen	$V_{f,total}$	Winding Angle θ	Ratio of $V_{f,winding}$ to $V_{f,total}$	Experimentally- and analytically-determined mechanical properties (MPa)										
				E_{Lt}	F_{Lt}	E_{Lc}	F_{Lc}	E_{Tt}	F_{Tt}	E_{Tc}	F_{Tc}	G_{LT}	F_{LT}	v_{LT}
Box-1	54.5%	84°	11.6%	31983	669	44003	459	15091	117	43020	445	4855	75.8	0.31
Box-2	54.5%	84°	42.8%	23421	481	38254	382	20370	340	37044	386	3564	62.8	0.30
Box-3	54.5%	84°	43.4%	27642	523	37354	375	20472	345	41207	348	3578	57.4	0.28
Box-4	54.5%	72°	32.5%	24604	491	35133	307	14099	256	40268	428	4213	80.8	0.29
Box-5	54.5%	n.a. (pultruded)		34215	779	39755	437	13128	34	36474	421	4531	71.9	0.33

GFRP SHORT COLUMNS

Materials and Test Set-Ups

The pullwound and pultruded GFRP short columns were made to have two types of heights, namely 50 and 400 mm, and they were both extracted from the intact part of those beams previously tested by present authors (Liu et al. 2023). The terminology ‘short’ used in this paper is to show their relatively shorter heights and not to indicate the slenderness of columns. With that said, the short column (SC) specimens were denoted as, for example, SC-50-1-1 for SC specimen with height of 50 mm, made of Box-1 material (see Table 1), and the first specimen of its type. The test set-ups of SC specimens are shown in Figure 2. A hydraulic jack with capacity of 1000 kN was used to apply the load to the top section of all SC specimens in the manner of displacement-control at a rate of 1 mm/min. During the

tests, the ultimate failure of all specimens cannot be obtained within a rational deformation region (due to the progressive failure to be discussed in following sections), and thus, all SC-50 specimens were loaded to a vertical deformation of 5 mm (at least), and all SC-400 specimens were loaded to a vertical deformation of 10 mm (at least). When the pre-designated vertical deformation was reached, the test was manually stopped.

A total of 15 SC-50 specimens were tested, namely three identical tests for each type of materials (i.e., Box-1, -2, -3, -4, and -5, as shown in Table 1). The SC-50 specimens were placed directly in between of a steel platform and the steel loading plate, as shown in Figure 2a. Given the friction between GFRPs and steel plates, no lateral movements were observed at the top and bottom sections of specimens. Thus, the boundary conditions of SC-50 specimens can be deemed as fixed conditions at both ends, except that the top end is allowed to move downward. To monitor the vertical deformation of SC-50 specimen, two linear variable differential transformers (LVDT) were installed at the loading plates, denoted as vertical LVDTs, and the average values of those two LVDTs were taken as the vertical deformation of specimen. In addition, to monitor the strain changes during the tests, digital image correlation (DIC) was used focusing on the front web plate having nominal width of 82 mm, and three strain gages were installed at the opposite web plate, spaced at 15 mm at the center.

A total of 13 SC-400 specimens were tested, namely three identical tests for each type of materials except for Box-1 having only one specimen. For SC-400 specimens, eight steel nuts were welded at the bottom platform and the top loading plate (four nuts at each side), to restrain the possible lateral movements of specimen, as shown in Figure 2b. Therefore, the boundary conditions of SC-400 specimens were kept the same with those of SC-50 specimens. Similar to SC-50 specimens, two vertical LVDTs were installed at the top loading plate to monitor the vertical deformation of specimen, and DIC and strain gages were respectively installed at front and back web plates of specimen to monitor the strain changes. In addition, two lateral LVDTs were installed near the top and bottom sections of SC-400 specimen to monitor the possible lateral movements.

a) 50-mm-high short column test (denoted as SC-50 specimens)

b) 400-mm-high short column test (denoted as SC-400 specimens)

c) Failure modes of 50-mm-high column

d) Failure modes of 400-mm-high column

Figure 2: Test set-ups and failure modes of short column specimens

Test Results of Short Columns

The failure modes of all SC-50 and -400 specimens are shown in Figures 2c and 2d, respectively, and the corresponding test results are presented in Table 2. In addition, the representative load-strain and load-lateral displacement curves of a SC-400 specimen are shown in Figure 3. From Figures 2c and 2d, it can be seen that all GFRP SC specimens failed due to end-section crushing. For relatively shorter specimens SC-50, excessive end-section crushing may also lead to damage of web plates at high load levels. On the other hand, for all SC-400 specimens, no damage was observed at web plates and only end-section crushing was observed. From Figure 3, the load-strain curves are linear until reaching the peak load P_{exp} , showing that there is no local buckling occurred during the test, and the load-lateral displacement curves show limited lateral displacements at both top and bottom ends of SC-400 specimen, with the greatest lateral displacement of 1.10 mm before reaching the peak load P_{exp} . Thus,

both the strains and lateral displacements can demonstrate that buckling and lateral flexure were not occurred in this test, which further validates the dominant failure mode of end-section crushing (i.e., a strength limit state).

Table 2: Experimental results of short columns

Specimen	d (mm)	b (mm)	t (mm)	P_{exp} (kN)	Avg P_{exp} (kN) (COV)	$\Delta @ P_{exp}$ (mm)	Δ_{max} (mm)	$F_{Lc,exp}$ (MPa)	$F_{Lc,coupon}$ (MPa)	$F_{Lc,exp} / F_{Lc,coupon}$	Avg $F_{Lc,exp} / F_{Lc,coupon}$ (COV)
SC-50-1-1	67.80	82.38	4.79	199	184 (0.07)	1.40	7.21	148	459	0.32	0.30 (0.07)
SC-50-1-2				188		1.67	8.51	140		0.30	
SC-50-1-3				169		1.59	6.00	125		0.27	
SC-400-1-1				182		5.43	17.80	135		0.29	
SC-50-2-1	67.81	82.24	4.75	152	142 (0.07)	1.89	10.75	114	382	0.30	0.28 (0.07)
SC-50-2-2				130		2.70	10.03	97		0.25	
SC-50-2-3				154		1.71	8.14	115		0.30	
SC-400-2-1				145		3.34	17.01	109		0.28	
SC-400-2-2				135		3.86	16.61	101		0.26	
SC-400-2-3				134		3.91	19.48	100		0.26	
SC-50-3-1	67.56	82.32	4.82	127	139 (0.08)	1.63	9.20	94	375	0.25	0.27 (0.08)
SC-50-3-2				143		1.56	10.16	106		0.28	
SC-50-3-3				125		1.81	10.87	93		0.25	
SC-400-3-1				148		3.31	14.42	110		0.29	
SC-400-3-2				150		6.55	16.71	111		0.30	
SC-400-3-3				142		3.22	16.99	105		0.28	
SC-50-4-1	67.83	82.41	4.87	155	153 (0.06)	1.54	11.37	113	307	0.37	0.36 (0.06)
SC-50-4-2				147		1.78	11.27	108		0.35	
SC-50-4-3				148		1.77	12.72	108		0.35	
SC-400-4-1				147		3.02	17.69	108		0.35	
SC-400-4-2				125*		3.93	16.70	91		0.30	
SC-400-4-3				169		3.74	17.25	123		0.40	
SC-50-5-1	67.54	81.82	4.70	244	243 (0.03)	1.73	11.37	186	437	0.43	0.42 (0.03)
SC-50-5-2				242		1.55	11.48	184		0.42	
SC-50-5-3				252		1.47	11.79	192		0.44	
SC-400-5-1				248		3.03	17.70	188		0.43	
SC-400-5-2				230		3.20	17.30	175		0.40	
SC-400-5-3				239		3.16	14.49	182		0.42	

* This data is deemed as an outlier, and thus, is removed.

Figure 3: Representative load-strain and load-lateral displacement curves of short column specimen (SC-400-4-1)

From Table 2, it is seen that the coefficients of variance (COV) of the average strength P_{exp} of SC-50 and SC-400 specimens are all less than 0.10, showing a good consistency between the SC specimens with two heights. Moreover, the compressive strength of those specimens made with Box-5 material is the highest, namely 243 kN, which is followed by Box-1 of 184 kN, Box-4 of 153 kN, Box-2 of 142 kN, and Box-3 of 139 kN. Such a trend actually does not agree with the longitudinal compressive

strength $F_{Lc,coupon}$ measured from small-scale coupon tests. Additionally, the compressive strength of five types of materials were calculated based on experimental results of short columns, denoted as $F_{Lc,exp}$ in Table 2. It is seen that the values of $F_{Lc,exp}$ are only about 0.27~0.42 of $F_{Lc,coupon}$. Evidently, there is a discrepancy between the material strength measured at coupon level and that measured at structural member level. It is noted that Wu et al. (2022) recently reported a similar discrepancy, with strength ratio of 0.37. The influential factors to this issue might include the local stress concentration and material imperfections (Wu et al. 2022), which, from another angle, can be considered as a scale effect between coupons and structural members.

The representative load-deformation curves of specimens SC-50 and SC-400 are shown in Figure 4. All the load-deformation curves are generally linear until reaching their peak loads. Then, the loads dropped by about 18~31%, and after the sudden drop, the loads were able to be maintained at a relatively high level, though they were gradually decreasing. With the failure mode of end-section crushing identified, it can be concluded that it is the progressive failure of material, in the manner of compression failure, led to the non-linear behavior of GFRP short columns after their peak loads. The high non-linearity of GFRP short columns observed in this work is different from those GFRP short columns reported by Alajarmeh et al. (2021) and Aksoylu et al. (2022), in which only the linear-elastic behavior with sudden brittle failure was observed.

Figure 4: Representative load-deformation curves of short column tests

GFRP BOLTED CONNECTIONS

Materials and Test Set-Ups

The structural behaviors of pullwound and pultruded GFRP bolted connections (BC) were investigated following ASTM D5961 (2017). A total of two types of BC specimens were fabricated, with the first one fabricated following the standard coupon of ASTM D5961, denoted as BC-plate specimens, and the second one designed by present authors based on ASTM D5961, denoted as BC-box specimens. A total of 15 BC-plate specimens were tested, with three identical tests for each type of materials (i.e., Box-1, -2, -3, -4 and -5, as shown in Table 1), and a total of 24 tests were conducted on 12 BC-box specimens, and each box specimen was tested twice, each at one web plate having nominal width of 82 mm. Test set-ups are shown in Figure 5. All BC specimens were single bolted with 6-mm-diameter steel bolt fastened by a torque of 7 N·m. An MTS universal testing machine with capacity of 300 kN was used to apply the tensile load to the bolted connection in the manner of displacement-control at a rate of 2 mm/min. DIC was used to monitor the strain change around the bolt. The pullwound composites have winding rovings placed close to transverse direction, which is expected to be able to improve the shear strength of bolted connections; nonetheless, the winding roving layer is found not in good contact with the longitudinal rovings, as reported by Liu et al. (2023). With that being said, the small-scale BC-plate specimen having standard width of 36 mm would cut off the winding rovings, and the winding roving layer may be pulled off from the coupon in the tests, compromising the shear strength of pullwound composites. In this regard, BC-box specimens were fabricated, with one side having a single bolt (i.e., test region) and the other side having four bolts (i.e., grip region). This BC-box specimen has winding rovings going around all the four web plates, and presumably, the winding rovings cannot be

easily pulled off from the section, thus ensuring the expected shear strength of pullwound composites. In addition, all tests were manually stopped when reaching the vertical deformation of 5 mm (at least) (measured by loading machine) for BC-plate specimens and 10 mm (at least) for BC-box specimens.

Figure 5: Test set-ups of bolted connections

Test Results of Bolted Connections

The typical failure modes of BC-plate specimens are shown in Figure 6. It can be seen that for BC-plate specimens the shear-out failure is the dominant failure mode, and for pullwound specimens—BC-plate-1, BC-plate-3, and BC-plate-4—winding rovings were pulled out from the specimens simultaneously with the shear-out of longitudinal rovings, which agrees with the findings from previous work of authors that winding rovings are not in good contact with longitudinal rovings due to the lack of resin at the interface. Provided the winding rovings were pulled out, the shear strength of pullwound composites is compromised.

Figure 6: Typical failure modes of BC-plate specimens

The typical failure modes of BC-box specimens are shown in Figure 7. It is observed that the longitudinal rovings first sheared out from sections, meanwhile the winding rovings continued sustaining the load. Then, winding rovings were gradually pulled out from the section. For BC-box specimens, the interface failure between different roving layers is not as prominent as that occurred for BC-plate specimens. In fact, for BC-box specimens the pull-out of winding rovings occurred after the shear-out of longitudinal rovings, and this can be evidenced by the length of pull-out and shear-out exhibited in Figures 6 and 7. In Figure 6, the length of pull-out of winding rovings and shear-out of longitudinal rovings are almost the same (see BC-plate-3 and BC-plate-4 in Figure 6), while in Figure 7, the length of shear-out is greater than that of pull-out (see BC-box-1 in Figure 7). Thus, winding rovings enabled an improved shear strength of GFRP bolted connections.

Figure7: Typical failure modes of BC-box specimens

Test results of all BC-plate and BC-box specimens are shown in Table 3. It is noted that the thickness t of plates under investigation are slightly different from one to another. Despite of having different plate thickness, it is seen that all BC-box specimens have higher shear-out strength $R_{sh,exp}$ than their corresponding BC-plate specimens, except for one case of BC-plate-1 and BC-box-1. Given the same

geometry of bolted connection, such an increase in shear strength can be attributed to the effective winding rovings.

Table3: Experimental results of bolted connections

Specimen	Thickness t (mm)	$R_{sh,exp}$ (kN)	Avg. $R_{sh,exp}$ (kN) (COV)	$F_{LT,coupon}$ (MPa)	$R_{sh,pred}$ (kN)	$R_{sh,pred} / R_{sh,exp}$	
BC-plate-1-1	4.79	8.26	7.97 (0.04)	75.8	7.62	0.92	
BC-plate-1-2	5.39	7.97			8.58	1.08	
BC-plate-1-3	4.58	7.67			7.29	0.95	
BC-box-1-1a	5.30	6.81	7.06 (n.a.)		8.44	1.24	
BC-box-1-1b	4.90	7.30			7.80	1.07	
BC-plate-2-1	4.22	5.20	5.49 (0.05)		62.8	5.57	1.07
BC-plate-2-2	5.70	5.48		7.52		1.37	
BC-plate-2-3	5.89	5.78		7.77		1.34	
BC-box-2-1a	4.40	4.15*	6.90 (0.16)	-		-	
BC-box-2-1b	5.60	1.09*		-		-	
BC-box-2-2a	5.30	6.16		6.99		1.14	
BC-box-2-2b	4.70	7.40		6.20		0.84	
BC-box-2-3a	5.20	8.24		6.86		0.83	
BC-box-2-3b	4.10	5.79		5.41		0.93	
BC-plate-3-1	4.77	5.89	5.49 (0.07)	57.4		5.75	0.98
BC-plate-3-2	4.56	5.41				6.77	1.25
BC-plate-3-3	4.33	5.17				5.22	1.01
BC-box-3-1a	6.20	8.59	7.95 (0.14)		7.47	0.87	
BC-box-3-1b	4.80	3.04*			-	-	
BC-box-3-2a	5.50	6.71			6.63	0.99	
BC-box-3-2b	5.00	8.56			6.03	0.70	
BC-plate-4-1	4.55	8.20	8.69 (0.05)		80.8	7.72	0.94
BC-plate-4-2	5.04	9.16				8.55	0.93
BC-plate-4-3	4.35	8.71				7.38	0.85
BC-box-4-1a	5.40	10.45	11.04 (0.09)			9.16	0.88
BC-box-4-1b	5.00	8.28*				-	-
BC-box-4-2a	4.60	11.45		7.81		0.68	
BC-box-4-2b	5.00	12.25		8.48		0.69	
BC-box-4-3a	5.40	10.03		9.16		0.91	
BC-box-4-3b	5.40	8.58*		-		-	
BC-plate-5-1	5.33	7.47	7.16 (0.07)	71.9		8.05	1.08
BC-plate-5-2	5.27	7.40				7.96	1.08
BC-plate-5-3	5.24	6.61				7.91	1.20
BC-box-5-1a	5.40	10.00	9.46 (0.09)		8.15	0.82	
BC-box-5-1b	4.60	8.79			6.95	0.79	
BC-box-5-2a	5.50	9.93			8.30	0.84	
BC-box-5-2b	5.50	10.69			8.30	0.78	
BC-box-5-3a	5.60	8.51			8.46	0.99	
BC-box-5-3b	4.30	8.85			6.49	0.73	

* This data is deemed as an outlier, and thus, is removed.

In addition, the shear-out strength R_{sh} of all BC specimens are calculated according to ASCE (2010), as shown in Eq. 1, and the predicted $R_{sh,pred}$ are shown in Table 3.

$$R_{sh} = 1.4 \left(e_1 - \frac{d_n}{2} \right) t F_{LT} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Where e_1 is the end distance, in this case $e_1 = 18$ mm; d_n is the nominal hole diameter, in this case $d_n = 6$ mm; t is the plate thickness; and F_{LT} is the in-plane shear strength of GFRP.

Figure 8 shows the representative load-deformation curves of BC-plate and BC-box specimens. It can be seen that all BC specimens exhibit a linear-elastic behavior until the peak loads. Then, the load suddenly dropped due to the partial shear-out of longitudinal rovings. With the cracks continued

propagating, the loads continued decreasing; nonetheless, specimens BC-box-1, BC-box-2, BC-box-3 and BC-box-5 were able to maintain their loads for relatively high deformations. The progressive failure of GFRPs, in the manner of shear failure, actually enabled the non-linear behavior of GFRP bolted connections (Feng et al. 2021).

Figure 8: Representative load-deformation curves of bolted connections

DISCUSSIONS

This paper is aimed to report the experimental program of an ongoing work on non-linear behavior of pultruded GFRP composites. Corresponding analytical and numerical programs are to be conducted. Based on the experimental observations reported in this paper, it can be concluded that pultruded GFRP members, at macroscopic level, could exhibit various extent of non-linearities when subjected to compression or shear force. Such a non-linear behavior is believed to be resulted from the synergistic effect of fiber-matrix architecture, fiber volume fractions, loading conditions, plate slenderness ratios, and material initial imperfections. In order to quantify the effect of each above factor, comprehensive numerical program must be conducted.

Existing design guides, such as ASCE (2010), EUR27666 (2016), CECS-692 (2020), have generally prescribed pultruded GFRP profiles as a linear-elastic material with brittle failure mode. Undoubtedly, this method is to yield conservative designs, whereas it has been greatly limiting the possible applications of this type of material. In many scenarios, steel structures are designed only allowing the linear-elastic behavior of material, and the plasticity is only designed for extreme loading conditions, such as high-degree earthquakes. Following the design philosophy of steel, the non-linear behavior of pultruded GFRPs may be of great potential for meeting the requirement for extreme loading conditions, though pultruded GFRPs are still designed with their linear-elastic properties for normal conditions. To achieve this goal, a number of experimental data is needed to support the development of design methods.

GFRP structural profiles, to date, can be manufactured with various techniques other than pultrusion, such as pullbraiding (Lebel and Nakai 2012), pullwinding (Liu et al. 2023), and curved-pultrusion (Liu et al. 2021). Through these techniques, hybrid roving architecture and non-linear structural geometry can be readily realized, both of which might permit non-linear behaviors of GFRP structures. Nonetheless, little work has been done on those new GFRP structural members as compared to the conventional pultruded GFRP profiles.

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the non-linear behaviors of pultruded GFRP composites were investigated through two series of experimental tests, one on GFRP short columns and the other one on GFRP bolted connections. These two experimental tests were designed to evaluate the progressive failure of GFRPs in the manner of compression and shear failure. Based on the experimental observations, the continued end-section crushing and shear-out failure could lead to the non-linear behaviors of GFRPs after reaching their peak loads, thus enabling high extent of deformation capacities (i.e., also known as the quasi-plastic

behaviors). The observed non-linear behaviors of GFRP composites may be able to meet the requirement for structural members subjected to extreme loading conditions, which would greatly expand the possible applications of GFRP composites.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.